

Many-valued logic and *syādvāda*

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In recent times Philosophers have used concepts and techniques of modern western logic to interpret *Syādvāda-saptabhaṅgīnaya* the epistemological form of *anekāntavāda*, which offer a sevenfold mode of predications or judgments. This is a fundamental theory of Jaina philosophy, unavailable in any other system of Indian philosophy. The modern logical concepts and techniques that have been used to understand the ancient Jaina doctrine of '*syāt*' were not available to ancient philosophers of India including the Jainas.

However, in this paper we intend consider mainly the application of many valued logic by S. L. Pandey.

Many-valued logic and *syādvāda*: S. L. Pandey's interpretation

Professor S. L. Pandey in his paper "*Nayavāda and Many-Valued Logic*" tries to understand *nayavāda* and *syādvāda*, which he regards as a species of *nayavāda*, in terms of many-valued logic (1).

S. L. Pandey assimilates the logic of *nayas* with Lukasiewiczian three-valued logic by exploiting the distinction between *pramāṇa*, *naya* and *durnaya* (2). The first question which S. L. Pandey wants to raise is: 'what is the truth-value of a *naya*'? Pandey consider the remarks of Malliṣeṇa in *Syādvādamañjarī* ["*sadeva sat syātsaditi tridhārtho miyeta durnītinayapramāṇeḥ / Yathārthadarśi tu nayapramāṇapathena durnītipatham tvamāsthah.*"] (3) — "*Syādvādamañjarī*, Verse no. 28.] and claims to following Malliṣeṇa in determining the truth value of a statement. Pandey says: "Malliṣeṇa distinguishes a *naya* from a *pramāṇa* on the one hand and from *durnaya* on the other. According to him a *pramāṇa* is true and a *durnaya* is false. Consequently, the truth value of a *naya* is different from the true and the false and is properly speaking 'indeterminate' or 'indefinite' or a 'third logical value'. The illustration of a *pramāṇa*, *durnaya* and *naya* are respectively (a) *syāt* words are ephemeral, (b) words are

ephemeral only and (c) words are ephemeral. A *naya* is not qualified with any particle (*nipāta*) but a *pramāṇa* is qualified with the particle '*syāt*' and a *durnaya* is qualified with the particle *eva* (or only). The false statement is called *ekāntavāda* or the statement of exclusive predication, while the true statement is called *syādavāda* or the statement of relative predication i.e., a statement under the perspectives of its truth-condition. Finally the unqualified or unmodified statement that is *naya* is ordinary or common sense statement that has a neutral truth-value which may be called the indeterminate truth-value"(4).

From this point of view S.L. Pandey inquires into the nature of this neutral truth value. What sort of a truth value is this? The straight answer to this question, according to him, is that it is an intermediate truth-value i.e., it is a truth-value which lies between truth and falsehood. In other words, the indeterminate truth-value is less true than the true and more true than the false. He therefore thinks that, the Jaina concept of the indeterminate truth-value, thus perfectly accords with the similar concept of Lukasiewicz's concept of indeterminate truth-value.

A question may be raised regarding the grounds for interpreting the indeterminate truth value of *naya* as the indeterminate truth value proposed by Lukasiewicz? This question is extremely relevant and may be disposed of, according to Pandey, on the consideration of following grounds:-

First Argument : Jaina logicians regards a *naya* neither as *pramāṇa* (true statement) nor as *apramāṇa* (false statement) but as approximation to *pramāṇa*. The terms they use are *pramāṇāṃśa* (aspects of *pramāṇa*) and *pramāṇaika-deśika* (a segment of *pramāṇa*). Both these words signify or presuppose the ontological category of the whole and parts. But Jaina philosophers themselves have made a clear-cut distinction between knowledge and reality (5) ["*pramāṇanayairadhigamaḥ*", 'knowledge is the means and reality is the end'. *Tattvārtha Sūtra*, 1-6, by Umāsvāti]. So the ontological category of the whole and parts cannot be applied, Pandey says, to the epistemic category of truth values or processes like *pramāṇa* and *naya*. *Nayas qua* knowledge differ *ipso facto* from things or real objects. On Pandey's view it is untenable therefore, to maintain that a *naya* is a part or segment of *pramāṇa*. The logical relation between *naya* and *pramāṇa* is based on their truth-values. Consequently, 'aspects of *pramāṇa* or segment of *pramāṇa* are to be understood as approximations to *pramāṇa*. In other words, the truth value of *naya* falls between the true and the false or it is removed from the false and approximates to the true. So, the Jaina concept of the truth-value of *naya* is logically the same as Lukasiewicz's concept of the indeterminate truth-value, Pandey concludes (6).

In this context Pandey, refers to Pandit Kailash Chandra Shastri who has also come to a similar conclusion in his Hindi translation of the *Nayavivarāṇa* portion of Vidyānanda's *Tattvārtha Śloka Vārtika* (7), for he says that the truth value of *naya* is true from one stand-point and false from another stand-point, i.e., it has two aspects — the aspect of the true and the aspect of the false. Lukasiewicz's concept of the indeterminate truth-value renders the truth-value of *nayas* meaningful. So, Pandey claims that the observation of Pt. Kailash Chandra Shastri is, in all likelihood, indicative of the position held by Lukasiewicz.

Second Argument: As for the second ground, S. L. Pandey cites the views of Akalaṅka and Vidyānanda in support of his view that the intermediate truth-value is to be understood in terms of the concept of probability. He observes that: Both Akalaṅka and Vidyānanda have a clear conception of Probability. Vidyānanda, for example, says, while commenting upon the *Aṣṭaśatī* of Akalaṅka that *prāmāṇya* or logical value of every *naya* is a probability value or a mid-way position between truth and falsehood or a position involving both truth and falsehood in various degrees. Prof. Mahendra Kumar Jaina has rightly understood this midway position as probability (8). Again, a *naya* is called *sunaya* or sound *naya* when its truth-value is intrinsic to itself and does not depend on any other *naya* (9). This means that there are *nayas* and hence *nayavāda* leads to a non-truth-functional many-valued logic of probability. But when the question is raised about the truth-values of only three statements which are respectively true, probable and false, then this logic of probabilities gives rise to a three valued logic. Further the Jainas are conceived this logic as truth-functional also, in as much as they have tried to seek truth-value relations among *nayas*, particularly between the three original *nayas* and the remaining four ones of the *naya saptabhaṅgī* Jaina logic is thus indicative of both a non-truth-functional many-valued logic of probabilities and a truth-functional three valued logic of which one type is the logic of Lukasiewicz. Our main concern, however, is, with the latter (10).

Third Ground: As for the third ground, Pandey cites the view of Mallavādin. He observes that, Mallavādin has designated the three original *nayas* as *vidhi*, *vidhiniyama* and *niyama* (11) which may be understood as the positive, indeterminate and negative statements. What is remarkable in this conception of Mallavādin is the point that he clearly conceived the three truth-values and classified statements according to their truth-values. He placed the indeterminate statement just below the true statement and above the false statement in the scale of decreasing truth-values. This is exactly what Lukasiewicz has done, Pandey concludes (12). Pandey claims, the truth-value of an indeterminate statement, according to Jainism and

Lukasiewicz is more than 'F' and less than 'T'.

Fourth Ground: As for the fourth ground, Pandey observes: Jaina logicians have made a clear distinction between *nayavākya* and *pramāṇavākya* or between *naya saptabhaṅgī* and *pramāṇa saptabhaṅgī*. The former is a table of seven statements each one of which has the truth-value I whereas the latter is a table of seven statements each one of which has the truth-value 'T' or 'I'. Now Jaina logicians have further displayed their correct grasp of three truth-functional operatives, namely negation, disjunction or alternation and conjunction. Negation (*niṣedha* or *pratiṣedha*) may be symbolized as '~', conjunction (*yugapadbhāva*) as '^' and disjunction (*kramabhāva*) as 'v'. Again suppose a statement P has the truth-value 'I'. Now the negation of P is also I. The conjunction of P and ~P is again I and the disjunction P and ~P, i.e., $P \vee \sim P$ is also I. statement of *naya saptabhaṅgī* are respectively P, ~P, $P \vee \sim P$ and $P \wedge \sim P$ and each one of them has the truth-value 'I'. The fifth statement is the conjunction of the first and the fourth statements, the sixth statement is the conjunction of the fourth statement and the second statement, and lastly the seventh statement is the conjunction of the fourth statement and the third statement (13). In this way, obviously according to the rule of conjunction the truth-value of all these three compound statements is I. So the table of seven *nayas* is like this:-

1. P where P is I
2. ~P which is I
3. $P \vee \sim P$ which is I
4. $P \wedge \sim P$ which is I
5. $P \wedge (P \wedge \sim P)$ which is I
6. $\sim P \wedge (P \wedge \sim P)$ which is I
7. $(P \vee \sim P) \wedge (P \wedge \sim P)$ which is I (14)

This table becomes logically verified if we maintain that the logic of *nayas* is a three valued logic of Lukasiewicz, Pandey says. Pandey confirms, "Surprisingly enough, the *naya saptabhaṅgī* challenges the law of excluded middle, because here $P \vee \sim P$ which is the classical formulation of the law is not a tautology as its truth-value is 'I' and not 'T'. It further challenges the law of contradiction because here ' $P \wedge \sim P$ ' which is the classical formulation of the law is

not false but I. It assumes that the truth value of a conjunction is the falsest, and that of a disjunction is the truest, of the truth values of its components. Now these epoch-making discoveries of Jaina logicians can be logically, though not historically, linked with the modern developments of three-valued logic" (15).

5.2. A critical estimate of Pandey's interpretation

(A) Pandey's main contention, stated as the **first ground**, is that the *nayas* as "approximation to *pramāṇa*" (or true statement) fall "between the true and the false". Therefore, they have a type of truth-value which is logically the same as Lukasiewicz's indeterminate truth-value (16). It may be pointed out that Lukasiewicz does not regard the indeterminate truth-value as "approximation to truth" (17). The indeterminate truth-value belongs to a statement, whose truth-value can not be determine either as true or as false because of the very nature of the statement. It therefore, has a third truth-value.

Ordinarily only two truth-values, namely, Truth and Falsity are admitted to a statement (or a proposition) and classical two-valued logic is based on this idea, so that every statement is either true or false (18).

In the last century Many-valued logic are developed which admit three or more truth-values to a proposition. The pioneering work in this field was inaugurated by J. Lukasiewicz who developed a three-valued logical system (19). He came to the idea that a proposition may have three truth-values from his examination of (Aristotle's problem of) future contingent statements. A future contingent statement is one, which is not necessarily true, nor is it impossible for it to be true. Such a statement may be true or may be false. For instance, 'there is a pen on the table' is a contingent proposition. It will be true if there is a pen on the table, false otherwise. In a future contingent statement, a contingent event is declared to happen in the future. As in Aristotle's example, 'there will be a sea-fight tomorrow'. The occurrence of the sea-fight tomorrow is a contingent matter, the sea-fight may happen tomorrow, it may not happen. Lukasiewicz's point is that as announced today the statement is neither true, nor false. But must have a third truth-value, which is different from truth and falsity (20).

Aristotle's solution to the problem was different. He held that the Law of Excluded Middle, according to which, in its semantic formulation, every proposition is either true or false, did not apply to future contingent statements. The concept of a third truth-value was a great contribution made by Lukasiewicz to logic.

In his paper "*Many-valued Systems of Propositional Logic*" (21), Lukasiewicz had already elaborated this position in this regard: "I can assume without contradiction that my presence in Warsaw at a certain moment of next year, e.g., at noon on 21st December, is at the present time determined neither positively nor negatively. Hence, it is possible, but not necessary, that I shall be present in Warsaw at the given time. On this assumption the proposition 'I shall be in Warsaw at noon on 21st December of next year', can at the present time be neither true nor false. For if it were true now, my future presence in Warsaw would have to be necessary, which is contradictory to the assumption. If it were false now, on the other hand, my future presence in Warsaw would be impossible, which is also contradictory to the assumption. Therefore, the proposition considered at the moment *neither true nor false* and must possess a third value, different from '0' or falsity and '1' or truth. This value we can designate by '½'." (22)

It is clear from what Lukasiewicz says that the third truth-value is not an "approximation to true"; nor is it something falling in between truth and falsity. Lukasiewicz also return to this problem in his book "*Aristotle's Syllogistic From the Standpoint of Modern Formal Logic*" where he held the same position with regard to future contingent statements.

(B) As for Pandey's contention, every *naya* is a probability value or a midway position between truth and falsity or a position involving both truth and falsehood in various degrees (23).

We may point out that the probability of a statement is always relative to the evidence produced and the probability is calculated on the basis of this evidence. For instance, a coin is tossed up and I say 'the coin will turn up Head', the probability of the coin turning up Head is '½' if the evidence produced is that out of ten tosses, 'the coins turned up Heads five times' its probability would be half. But if the evidence produced is that out of hundred tosses, the same coin has turned up Heads thirty-five times then its probability of the statement would be 35/100, and *relative to the evidence, the probability statements are correct or true.*

So, we see that a probability statement does not always occupy 'a midway position' between truth and falsity or 'a position involving both truth and falsehood in various degrees'.

The Jaina philosophers have not raised the question of an evidence when they talk about *naya*. They only consider certain point of view or aspects from which something is viewed (24). Points of view or aspects etc. cannot be regarded as evidence adduced in support of a

statements, probable or otherwise.

(C) As a third reason in support of his view Pandey refers to Mallavādin, who, according to Pandey, has designated the three *nayas* of the Jaina — *vidhi*, *vidhiniyama* and *niyama*, as original, which may be, understood in his opinion, as the positive, indeterminate, and negative statements.

A reading on Mallavādin '*Dvādaśāranayacakra*' reveals no such three *nayas* as *original*. If we are to regard the *nayas* as original on Mallavādin's view they should be *vidhi* and *niyama*. The other as we can see, would be arise out of the combinations and repetitions of this two. Mallavādin fixes up twelve *nayas* in his '*Dvādaśāranayacakra*' which are as follows:-

1. *vidhi*
2. *vidhervidhi*
3. *vidhervidhiśca niyamaśca*
4. *vidherniyama*
5. *vidhiśca niyamaśca*
6. *vidhi niyamaurvidhi*
7. *vhiniyamarvidhiniyama*
8. *vidhiniyamau-niyama*
9. *niyamah*
10. *niyamasca-vidhi*
11. *niyamasya-vidhiniyamau*
12. *niyamasya-niyamah (25)*

But he does not stop here. According to Mallavādin every *naya* is defective that is why he goes on to a next *naya* to overcome the defect which again turns out to be defective. So, he is not satisfied with the list of the twelve *nayas*. He says that he again starts from the first and goes on in a circle or a *cakra*. This process goes on (26). His aim is to show that we cannot get a total view of reality but only get a certain aspect or partial view. However, painstaking efforts you may take, you do not get a total view of reality, by piecing together different points of view

or aspects.

Contrary to Pandey's view, Lukasiewicz does not conceive of the indeterminate statement (or truth-value) 'just below the true statement and above the false statement in the scale of decreasing the truth-value'. There is no trace of such a thing in Lukasiewicz's three-valued logic.

(D) A *naya*, as we have explained, in the preceding chapter, is a partial statement and does not express the whole truth. This is not the same thing as to say that a *naya* is indeterminate. A *naya* expresses a truth although partial (27). An indeterminate statement is neither true nor false. A *naya* expresses a truth however, truncated. But an indeterminate statement does nothing of this kind. So, the basic assumption about *naya* from which Pandey starts, seems to be based on a mistake. And, therefore his whole construction of *naya-saptabhaṅgī* in terms of the three-valued logic totters.

Now let us look at its construction. *Vidhirvidhiśca niyamaśca* is the third *bhaṅga* in the scheme of *naya*. According to the Jaina logicians this is '*krama-vidhi-pratiśedha-kalpanā*' (or *astināsti ca*). The Jaina logicians make it clear that a *kramabhāva* means successiveness --- something is viewed from a certain point of view and then from a different point of view. So, both are there, one coming after another (28). Let us try to make the point clear.

By considering a proposition 'there is a pen on the table', the *kramabhāva* yields two different propositions 'in this part of the table there is a pen' and 'in other part of the table there is no pen'. The former may be symbolized by 'p', the latter by 'q'. So the third *bhaṅga* should be symbolized that 'p . q' instead of 'p v ~q'.

Disjunction or alternation can nowhere be found in *kramabhāva*, which means, both in this case, one after the other. This meaning can be accommodated by using conjunction in the way we have just shown.

In support of the fourth *bhaṅga*, Pandey says, 'p ^ ~p' is the 'classical formulation' of the law of Contradiction. Such a formulation of the law of contradiction cannot be found in western logic. The classical formulation of this law is stated as '~(p.~p)' (29). So, the question of Pandey's interpretation of the fourth *bhaṅga* challenging the classical law of contradiction does not arise at all. It is obvious that Pandey's argument is based on a grave mistake.

Moreover, the ground for his interpretation posing a challenge to the classical law of

contradiction is that, it turns out I (indeterminate) and not F (false) on his interpretation. All the laws of logic are tautologous or logically true (30) and can never turn out false. It will have been very strange indeed the law of contradiction were false, as Pandey seems to think. How can anything be called a law in logic or, for that matter, in any science, if it is false?

Let us now consider Pandey's interpretation of *pramāṇa- saptabhaṅgī*. Every statement of *pramāṇa- saptabhaṅgī* is prefaced by '*syāt*' (31). Now according to Pandey, '*syāt* is a semantic qualifier. But it also includes the syntactic quantifier, and may be understood in the sense of the Existential quantifier, as statements qualified by *syāt* are particular statements and not universal statements' (32).

What Pandey says here lacks clarity. Pandey does not explain the difference between *syāt*'s being a semantic qualifier and also including a syntactic quantifier, in the sense of the existential quantifier. Now, since he brings in the existential quantifier, the question is pertinent as to what variables the quantifier binds and what predicate the variables attach too. Until the existential quantifier is brought to the force, for the proposition "*syāt* cows are white" and the full quantificational form of the proposition is stated clearly, his interpretation suffers from the defect of unclarity and this infects the whole construction of his *pramāṇa- saptabhaṅgī* — making it, it seems to us, unworthy of profitable use.

It should be remembered that, a proposition may contain several quantifiers (33). Pandey's existential quantifier 'concealed' in the '*syāt*' in the prenex position may bind a variable attached to a predicate different from 'cow' and 'white', and may leave the universality of 'all cows are white' intact which would require a universal quantifier.

It may appear to us that in his argument Pandey assumes that the existential quantifier, produced by '*syāt*' in '*syāt* all cows are white' binds a variable attached to the predicates 'cow' and 'white' turning the proposition 'all cows are white' into 'some cows are white'. The negation of 'all cows are white' is 'some cows are not white'. Now, 'some cows are not white' is itself an existential proposition and has already a quantifier and a variable attached to 'cow' and 'white' which, with the aid of the negation sign '~', is sufficient to take care of it. Then what is the function of the existential quantifier produced by '*syāt* all cows are not white' (logically equivalent to '*syāt* some cows are not white') in the second *bhaṅga*? It would have no function there and remain idle, which is logically an unacceptable position.

Now we come to the fourth *bhaṅga* - '*syāt* all cows are white and all cows are not white'

(*syāt avaktavya*) in which the *syāt* produces only one existential quantifier. The trouble here is that the two proposition conjoined by 'and', in this particular instance, requires two quantifiers and the one quantifier the '*syāt*' produces cannot do duty for both. So, we have to use another existential quantifier for the second conjunct 'all cows are not white'.

So the full quantificational formulation of the fourth *bhaṅga* '*syāt* all cows are white and all cows are not white' is as follows:

$(\exists x) (x \text{ is a cow and } x \text{ is white}) \text{ and } (\exists y) (y \text{ is a cow and } y \text{ is not white}).$

Now the whole conjunction is a true proposition and there is nothing expressible or indescribable or *avaktavya* about it. The two conjuncts can be asserted simultaneously conjoined by and without any fear of contradiction or inexpressibility or indescribability. So Pandey's interpretation of '*syāt*' fails to do justice to the fourth *bhaṅga* and takes the *avaktavya* element completely out of the Jaina *Syādvāda*.

What happens if the proposition in question prefaced by *syāt* is a singular proposition like 'Mallīṣeṇa is a philosopher'. The '*syāt*' in '*Syāt* Mallīṣeṇa is a philosopher' produces, on Pandey's interpretation, an existential quantifier which has nothing to do in this case, for a singular proposition like the one above, does not require the services of any quantifier at all (34). This is also a logically intolerable situation.

So Pandey's interpretation of *pramāṇa-saptabhaṅgī* seems to be deeply flawed.

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